

ROLE OF NIRGUNDI TAILA MATRA BASTI IN ACUTE FISSURE-IN-ANO (PARIKARTHIKA): A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Parikarthika is one among the common anorectal disorders described in Ayurveda, clinically comparable to acute fissure-in-ano. It is characterized by severe cutting pain during defecation, burning sensation, and occasional bleeding per rectum. Modern management provides temporary symptomatic relief, whereas Ayurvedic treatment aims at healing and recurrence prevention. The present case report aims to evaluate the efficacy of Ayurvedic management in acute fissure-in-ano. A 32-year-old male patient presented with severe pain during defecation, burning sensation, constipation, and streaks of bleeding per rectum for 10 days. Clinical examination revealed a fresh posterior midline fissure-in-ano. The patient was managed through a comprehensive Ayurvedic treatment protocol that included Nidana Parivarjana, internal medications, and local therapy with nirgundi taila matra basti, along with

Avagaha Swedana. Complete healing of the fissure was achieved within 14 days, with marked relief in pain, burning sensation, and bleeding. Pain was reduced from 8/10 to 1/10 within 14 days. No recurrence was observed during a follow-up period of two months.

KEYWORDS: Parikarthika, Acute fissure-in-ano, Nirgundi Taila, Matra Basti, Avgah-sweda, Ayurveda.

INTRODUCTION

Parikarthika is described in Ayurvedic classics as a condition characterized by cutting pain in guda pradesha. It closely resembles fissure-in-ano in modern surgery. Acute fissure commonly occurs due to passage of hard stool leading to tear in anoderm and reflex sphincter spasm.

Conventional management includes stool softeners, topical anesthetics, and surgery in resistant cases. Ayurveda offers various conservative modalities including Taila Prayoga and Basti Chikitsa.

Nirgundi (*Vitex negundo*) possesses anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antimicrobial, and wound-healing activities. Hence, Nirgundi Taila was selected for Matra Basti in this case.

CASE REPORT

Patient Information

- Name: XXX
- Age/Sex: 32 years/Male
- OPD/IPD No.: XXXXX
- Date: XX/XX/2026

Chief Complaints

- Severe pain during defecation since 10 days
- Burning sensation in anal region
- Constipation
- Streaks of bleeding per rectum

History of Present Illness

Patient was apparently normal 10 days back, after passage of hard stool he developed severe cutting pain during defecation associated with burning sensation and occasional bleeding.

Past History

- No history of diabetes mellitus
- No hypertension
- No previous anorectal surgery

Personal History

- Mixed diet
- Inadequate water intake
- Irregular bowel habits

CLINICAL FINDINGS**Local Examination**

- Fresh fissure at posterior midline (6 o'clock position)
- Sphincter spasm present
- Tenderness present

Systemic Examination

- Pulse: 78/min
- BP: 122/86 mmHg
- Afebrile

DIAGNOSIS**Ayurvedic Diagnosis**

Parikarthika.

Modern Diagnosis

Acute fissure-in-ano.

THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTION

Treatment	Dose	Duration
Nirgundi Taila Matra Basti	20 mL OD	14 days
Triphala Churna	5 g HS	14 days
Awgah sweda	Twice daily	14 days

Dietary Advice

- High-fiber diet
- Plenty of fluids
- Avoid spicy and constipating food

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Symptom	BT	AT
Pain	Severe	Mild
Burning sensation	Severe	Absent

Bleeding	Present	Absent
Constipation	Present	Improved
Sphincter spasm	Present	Reduced

RESULTS

Significant symptomatic improvement was observed within 14 days. Pain and burning sensation reduced considerably with cessation of bleeding. Local examination showed healing of fissure with reduction in sphincter spasm.

TABLE NO. 1: ASSESSMENT OF CLINICAL PARAMETERS BEFORE AND AFTER TREATMENT.

Sr. No.	PARAMETER	DAY 1	DAY 7	DAY 14
1.	Pain(VAS)	8/10	6/10	1/10
2.	Bleeding grade	3	1	0
3.	Sphincter Spasm	Grade 3	Grade 2	Grade 0

(VAS = Visual Analogue Scale)

Figure 1: Acute fissure-in-ano at posterior midline.(Before treatment).

Figure 2: Healed fissure after 14 days of Ayurvedic management.(After treatment).

DISCUSSION

Parikarthika is primarily caused by dietary and behavioral factors that aggravate Vata and Pitta dosha, leading to dryness, constipation, and ulcer formation in the anal canal. Excessive intake of spicy, sour, and dry food, suppression of natural urges, irregular bowel habits, and psychological stress are the major contributing factors.

Nidana Parivarjana plays a vital role in both treatment and prevention of recurrence.

Triphala churna helps in regulating bowel movements and pacifying Apana Vata.

Avagaha Swedana helps in reducing pain, sphincter spasm, and improves local circulation.

Nirgundi Taila possesses Vata-Kapha Shamaka, Shothahara, and Vedanasthapana properties which help in reducing sphincter spasm, pain and promotes faster healing of the fissure and provides symptomatic relief. In modern medicine, fissure-in-ano is associated with hypertonicity of the internal anal sphincter, leading to reduced blood supply and delayed healing. The Ayurvedic approach focuses on correcting the underlying pathology by pacifying Vata and Pitta dosha. Nirgundi Taila ingredients exhibit anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and wound-healing actions, which promote rapid epithelialization of the fissure. Avagaha Swedana helps in reducing sphincter spasm, improving local circulation, and relieving pain. The combined effect of internal medications and local therapy provides holistic management and prevents recurrence. Thus, the present case supports the potential of Ayurvedic management as an effective non-surgical approach in the treatment of acute fissure-in-ano.

CONCLUSION

Acute fissure-in-ano is a painful anorectal condition that significantly affects daily activities. Ayurvedic management, focusing on the correction of causative factors, bowel regulation, and local wound-healing therapies, provides effective and safe result. Nirgundi Taila Matra Basti showed encouraging results in the management of acute fissure-in-ano. It may be considered as a safe and effective conservative Ayurvedic approach for Parikarthika.

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